

Research Article

Effects of an ICT-Based Chinese Qigong Baduanjin Exercise Support Program on Self-Efficacy and Motivation to Promote Long-Term Practice for Hypertension Prevention in Adults

Meng Liu¹, Xiaoyu Wu^{2*}, Kiyoko Tokunaka³ and Miwa Yamamoto⁴

¹Graduate Department of Medicine, Division of Nursing Science, Kagawa University, Japan

²Kagawa Prefectural University of Health Sciences, School of Nursing, Kagawa Japan

³Department of Nursing, Kyoto Koka Women's University, Kyoto, Japan

⁴Department of Medicine, School of Nursing, Kagawa University, Kagawa, Japan

Abstract

In 2021, an ICT-Based Chinese Qigong Baduanjin (hereafter referred to as Baduanjin) Exercise Support Program was developed with the aim of preventing hypertension in adults by promoting the sustained practice of Baduanjin. Regular engagement in Baduanjin, a traditional exercise grounded in Chinese medicine, is believed to contribute to hypertension prevention; however, maintaining long-term adherence requires sufficient self-efficacy and motivation.

This study was conducted to evaluate the program's effectiveness in enhancing participants' self-efficacy and motivation. A total of 81 adults aged 18 and over who provided informed consent participated (ICT-based intervention group: 41; paper-based intervention group: 40). Outcomes were assessed using the General Self-Efficacy Scale

(GSES), the ARCS motivation model (Attention, Relevance, Confidence, Satisfaction), and qualitative responses to open-ended questions.

A comparative analysis was performed between the ICT-based and paper-based intervention groups. The results were as follows:^① Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in all four ARCS motivational factors were observed between participants with high and low GSES, with higher motivation in the high-GSES group.^② In the ICT-based intervention group, significant post-intervention improvements ($p < 0.05$) were found in GSES, one motivation item, and two confidence-related items.^③ Qualitative responses further supported increases in both self-efficacy and motivation.

These findings suggest that the ICT-based Baduanjin exercise support program effectively enhances psychological factors that are essential for the long-term continuation of Baduanjin and thereby has the potential to contribute to hypertension prevention.

Keywords: Exercise Support Program; GSES; ICT (Information and Communication Technology); Motivation

Background

According to the 2018 Revised Chinese Guidelines for the Prevention and Management of Hypertension, the prevalence of hypertension in the Chinese population continues to rise. The guidelines emphasize the necessity of integrating exercise into daily life as part of healthy lifestyle interventions through communication technologies such as media and websites [1]. Furthermore, the Healthy China 2030 Plan highlights that compared to other industries, the medical sector demonstrates a particularly strong fundamental demand for artificial intelligence applications and encourages the development of scientific exercise programs [2]. In this context, self-managed exercise as a lifestyle intervention plays an increasingly important role in controlling hypertension. With rapid economic development, technological advancement, and population aging, attention has been growing toward convenient and efficient telemedicine solutions.

Baduanjin, a traditional Chinese qigong exercise, is a full-body routine that combines slow movements and breathing techniques. Its health benefits have been substantiated by numerous studies, particularly among groups who practiced continuously for more than eight weeks. These studies have shown significant reductions in blood pressure, improvements in psychological well-being, and enhanced physical flexibility and balance [3]. However, these benefits are not achievable through short-term practice; a sustained period of engagement is required. Therefore, the continued practice of Baduanjin is essential to maximize its health benefits. Psychological factors, especially motivation and self-efficacy, are considered critical to sustaining engagement [4]. When individuals perceive value in Baduanjin (motivation) and believe in their ability to practice it (self-efficacy), they are more likely to incorporate it into daily life and form a lasting habit. For lifestyle-related diseases such as hypertension—where preventive behavior tends to be postponed—establishing easy-to-maintain and sustainable exercise habits is particularly important. Thus, intervention

*Corresponding author: Xiaoyu Wu, Department of Health Sciences, Kagawa Prefectural University of Health Sciences, Kagawa Japan, Email: u-s@kagawa-puhs.ac.jp

Citation: Liu M, Wu X, Tokunaka K, Yamamoto M (2025) Effects of an ICT-Based Chinese Qigong Baduanjin Exercise Support Program on Self-Efficacy and Motivation to Promote Long-Term Practice for Hypertension Prevention in Adults. HSOA J Altern Complement Integr Med 11: 597.

Received: May 23, 2025; **Accepted:** June 03, 2025; **Published:** June 09, 2025

Copyright: © 2025 Liu M, et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

programs that aim to enhance motivation and self-efficacy are expected to produce public health benefits by contributing to hypertension prevention.

To date, several exercise support programs utilizing information technologies (such as internet and digital tools) have been developed to promote physical activity. However, there is still a lack of empirical evidence demonstrating the effectiveness of ICT-based exercise support programs, and their nationwide implementation remains limited. According to Suzuki, e-learning materials based on the ARCS motivation model and Gagné's Nine Events of Instruction—educational design theories supporting the human information processing process—can be developed to be efficient, effective, and engaging, thus promoting learners' motivation to adopt physical activity [5,6]. In addition, Ding Dong proposed that to improve the quality of social medical services in telemedicine, the medical industry should actively promote telehealth education based on e-learning [7]. To address these challenges, in June 2021, developed an ICT-based Baduanjin exercise support program incorporating the principles of andragogy, the theory of adult learning [8].

Based on this, a quasi-experimental study was launched in July 2021 to evaluate whether the ICT-based Baduanjin Exercise Support Program effectively supports the integration of exercise into the daily lives of adults.

Objective

The effectiveness of an ICT-based Baduanjin Exercise Support Program was evaluated in this study.

Overview of the ICT-Based Baduanjin Exercise Support Program

An overview of the ICT-based Baduanjin Exercise Support Program was presented in figure 1. The key features of this program included the use of EDEN Corporation's e-learning platform, through which ease of management was facilitated and personalized information was provided. In addition, group learning—characteristic of adults.

Figure 1: Overview of the ICT-Based Baduanjin Exercise Support Program.

Methods

Participants

In this study, participants were divided into two groups—an ICT-based intervention group and a paper-based intervention group—to compare the effects of the intervention. The methods and procedures for group allocation are described below.

Recruitment and preliminary survey

To select study participants, community groups in China were chosen, and approval was obtained from the district office and

community group administrators. Through WeChat, community administrators were asked to introduce the researchers to potential participants in advance. Additionally, adults aged 18 and older who were interested in health promotion through Baduanjin were recruited via local health centers and online bulletin boards. Prior to participation, informed consent was obtained, and basic demographic information (such as gender, health status, and experience with smartphones or digital devices) was collected.

Eligibility criteria

Participants were included if they met the following criteria:

- Adults aged 18 years or older.
- No regular exercise habits within the past six months, aside from residential community activities.
- Ability to communicate verbally.
- Independence in activities of daily living.
- Absence of physical disabilities affecting exercise.
- Ability to operate a smartphone, tablet, or computer.

Group allocation procedure

Based on the collected demographic information, stratified randomization was used to allocate participants into groups in a balanced manner. Specifically, stratification factors such as gender and other relevant characteristics were used to randomly assign participants to the ICT-based intervention group: 41; paper-based intervention group: 40.

Study period

The study was conducted from June 2021 to July 2021.

Flow of the Baduanjin Exercise Support Program Intervention

- Pre-intervention Guidance for the Baduanjin Exercise Support Program

The following steps were carried out prior to the intervention:

- The effectiveness of Baduanjin in preventing hypertension was explained.
- The benefits of exercise for hypertension prevention were outlined.
- Instruction on how to use the e-learning exercise support system was provided.
- Personal goals were set.
- Guidance on how to learn and perform Baduanjin exercises was offered.

Implementation of the Baduanjin Exercise Support Program

For the ICT-based intervention group (as shown in figure 2):

- Participants recorded daily exercise impressions, physical conditions, and blood pressure on a designated sheet. Based on this information, necessary messages were sent by researchers, and relevant information was shared with all participants when appropriate.

- Mid-term and final reflections were conducted. Group discussions were held to promote peer learning and enhance motivation. Researchers facilitated these sessions and provided support for future exercise planning.
- Upon completion of the program, certificates of completion were automatically distributed to participants.

For the paper-based intervention group (as shown in figure 3):

- Exercise support videos and daily recording sheets were distributed via WeChat. Participants recorded their impressions, activity status, and blood pressure, and submitted photos of the completed sheets weekly.
- One-on-one reflection sessions were conducted at the Midterm and final stages. During these sessions, impressions, activity status, and blood pressure data were discussed, and possible solutions for future exercise challenges were considered.

Figure 2: Flow Diagram of the ICT Intervention Group.

Figure 3: Flow Diagram of the Paper Intervention Group.

Survey Content

- Before and after the program, participants were assessed using the Chinese version of the GSES. This scale, originally developed by Schwarzer et al., in 1981 and translated by Zhang Jianxin and Schwarzer in 1995, has been widely used in China with confirmed reliability and validity [9].
- Following the program, participants were evaluated using the ARCS Motivation Mode, developed by Guo Dejun in 2000 based on Keller’s ARCS motivation model. This questionnaire has also demonstrated reliability and validity [10].
- In addition, participants’ free-text responses were collected and organized at the Initial, Midterm, and Final.

Ethical Considerations

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Graduate School of Nursing at Kyoto Koka Women’s University (Approval No. 20MM3). The purpose, methodology, voluntary nature of participation, the right to withdraw, privacy protection, data handling and management, potential benefits and risks, and publication of results were explained both in writing and verbally. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to the commencement of the study.

Results

Basic Characteristics of the Study Participants

The basic characteristics of the participants were presented in table 1. Among the 81 total participants, the ICT-based intervention group consisted of 41 individuals whose average age was in their 40s (± 12.945). This group included 8 males (19.5%) and 33 females (80.5%). The paper-based intervention group, which consisted of 40 individuals, had an average age in the 20s (± 10.952), with 12 males (30%) and 28 females (70%).

Category	Subcategory	ICT-based intervention group (N = 41)	Paper-Based Intervention Group (N = 40)
Age	Minimum	20	10
	Maximum	70	50
	Mean	47.8	26.75
	Standard Deviation	12.945	10.952
	Gender		
	Male (%)	8 (19.5%)	12 (30%)
	Female (%)	33 (80.5%)	28 (70%)

Table 1: Basic Characteristics of Study Participants.

Relationship between GSES and the Four Factors of the ARCS Motivation Model After the Implementation of the Exercise Support Program

1)A Mann–Whitney U test was conducted to compare ARCS motivation model scores between participants with low and high post-intervention GSES scores. It was found that the mean rank of the low-GSES group was 15.79, while that of the high-GSES group was 23.22, indicating a significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.038$). However, no significant differences were observed between the low- and high-GSES groups for the following 26 ARCS items: A2, A21, A24, A27, A34, R11, R23, R28, R35, R38, R44, R49, C1, C22, C30, C37, C39, C42, C45, C48, S14, S18, S25, S29, S40, and S43 ($p > 0.05$). Aside from these items, significant differences were found in the overall ARCS motivation model scores and the remaining individual items between the low- and high-GSES groups ($p < 0.05$). The detailed results were provided in table 2. The increase in GSES and ARCS scores does not directly indicate differences between groups; however, the development of a positive attitude toward exercise and a willingness to continue suggests the potential for strengthening future hypertension prevention behaviors.

A Kruskal–Wallis H test was applied to examine differences in ARCS motivation model factor scores among four subgroups within the ICT-based intervention group, categorized by changes in GSES scores before and after the intervention. Significant differences

Item	Mean Rank		Mann-Whitney	
	Low Group (N = 21)	High Group (N = 16)	z	p
A2. If the instructor's explanations are vivid, it will affect my interest in learning.	16.67	22.06	-1.66	0.098
A4. If the instructor frequently uses visual aids like pictures and slides, it will affect my interest in learning.	16.9	21.75	-1.47	0.143
A10. If the instructor includes interesting stories related to the content, it will affect my interest in learning.	15.86	23.13	-2.39	0.017
A12. If the instructor allows us to explore the secrets of maintaining exercise by ourselves, it will affect my interest in learning.	15.36	23.78	-2.53	0.011
A15. If I get the chance to speak or demonstrate at a seminar, it will affect my interest in learning.	16	22.94	-2.08	0.037
A21. If the instructor frequently provides interesting information about exercise to stimulate curiosity, it will affect my interest in learning.	16.45	22.34	-1.85	0.065
A24. If interesting activities such as group competitions or discussions are included, it will affect my interest in learning.	16.76	21.94	-1.53	0.126
A27. If the instructor often uses vivid examples for teaching, it will affect my interest in learning.	17.21	21.34	-1.34	0.181
A33. If the instructor's teaching method is clear and focused, this will affect my interest.	15.48	23.63	-2.72	0.006
A34. If the instructor lets us explain the material and summarize the rules ourselves, this will affect my learning interest.	16.5	22.28	-1.78	0.076
Total A	15.55	23.53	-2.25	0.025
R3. If I understand that what I'm learning now is crucial for my future health, it will affect my interest in learning.	15.62	23.44	-2.47	0.013
R7. If I can stick to exercising well, it will improve my physical fitness and affect my interest in learning.	14.62	24.75	-3.14	0.002
R11. If the new knowledge connects with what I've already learned, it will affect my interest in learning.	17.19	21.38	-1.4	0.162
R13. If I can maintain daily exercise to stay healthy, it will affect my interest in learning.	15.64	23.41	-2.44	0.015
R16. If the instructor frequently asks me questions or gives me opportunities to express myself, it will affect my interest in learning.	16.29	22.56	-2.2	0.028
R19. If the instructor is always available to answer questions, it will affect my interest in learning.	41.45	40.54	-2.03	0.042
R23. If the teaching pace is neither too fast nor too slow, it will affect my interest in learning.	20.69	16.78	-1.19	0.236
R28. Knowing that daily exercise helps me stay healthy in the community will affect my interest in learning.	16.5	22.28	-1.8	0.072
R35. If I get to be a Mini instructor, this will affect my learning interest.	16.33	22.5	-1.82	0.068
R38. If I can attend exchange meetings and learn with other participants, this will affect my learning interest.	16.43	22.38	-1.74	0.082
R44. When we have questions, the instructor doesn't rush to answer but lets us think or discuss first, which will affect my learning interest.	17.9	20.44	-0.78	0.438
R47. If I realize that learning this exercise instruction well is helpful for learning other healthy activities, this will affect my learning interest.	16.21	22.66	-2.19	0.029
R49. If I keep regular exercise, I may be awarded the title of "Excellent Exercise Student." This belief will affect my learning interest.	17.07	21.53	-1.32	0.186
Total R	15.9	23.06	-2.01	0.045
C1. When I encounter difficulties in maintaining exercise, receiving timely encouragement from the instructor and regaining confidence will affect my interest in learning.	17.4	21.09	-1.17	0.242
C5. Realizing that success in exercise comes from effort rather than luck will affect my interest in learning.	14.9	24.38	-2.92	0.004
C8. I believe that if I keep trying, I will succeed, this belief will affect my interest in learning.	14.43	25	-3.22	0.001
C17. If the instructor guides us to apply exercises to real-life situations, it will affect my interest in learning.	15.55	23.53	-2.51	0.012
C22. If the instructor asks us to warm up before exercising and confirms relevant issues, it will affect my interest in learning.	18.38	19.81	-0.43	0.669
C26. If I can maintain good health, it will affect my interest in learning.	16.29	22.56	-2.12	0.034
C30. When the instructor says, "constant effort brings success," it will affect my interest in learning.	16.86	21.81	-1.48	0.138
C31. When encountering difficulties, if the instructor patiently demonstrates and explains, this will affect my learning interest.	16.24	22.63	-2.06	0.04
C37. If the instructor guides us to assess our learning in stages to increase self-awareness, this will affect my learning interest.	16.55	22.22	-1.75	0.081
C39. If I can set learning goals based on my actual situation, and the goals are neither too easy nor too difficult, this will affect my learning interest.	17.17	21.41	-1.3	0.193
C41. The instructor says that scoring well in daily exercise doesn't mean we've learned everything and encourages continued effort. This will affect my learning interest.	15.14	24.06	-2.6	0.009
C42. If the instructor often points out my weaknesses and believes I can improve, this will affect my learning interest.	16.6	22.16	-1.79	0.073

C45. The instructor requires us to independently complete daily regular exercise, which will affect my learning interest.	17.43	21.06	-1.22	0.222
C48. If I fail to maintain daily exercise and the instructor asks me to reflect on whether I'm working hard enough, this will affect my learning interest.	21.36	15.91	-1.63	0.104
Total C	15.6	23.47	-2.2	0.028
S6. If I can learn first and help other participants, it will affect my interest in learning.	15.74	23.28	-2.32	0.02
S9. Receiving praise or rewards from the instructor for daily exercise will affect my interest in learning.	14.93	24.34	-2.89	0.004
S14. When I make mistakes in maintaining exercise, the instructor writes comments like "I believe you can correct this"—this will affect my interest in learning.	16.93	21.72	-1.45	0.147
S18. If the instructor reviews and corrects our exercise performance in a timely manner, helping us understand our mistakes, it will affect my interest in learning.	16.5	22.28	-1.74	0.082
S20. When the instructor encourages my small improvements, it will affect my interest in learning.	16.1	22.81	-2.13	0.034
S25. If attending a seminar doesn't make me nervous, it will affect my interest in learning.	18.14	20.13	-0.63	0.53
S29. When I open feedback emails from the instructor, seeing "good" evaluations frequently affects my interest in learning.	16.57	22.19	-1.72	0.086
S32. When learning new knowledge, if the instructor constantly encourages and supports us, this will affect my learning interest.	15	24.25	-3.04	0.002
S36. If I can learn about every bit of progress from the instructor in a timely manner, this will affect my learning interest.	15.74	23.28	-2.42	0.016
S40. If my performance in the exercise instruction process is fully recognized by the instructor, this will affect my learning interest.	17.62	20.81	-0.99	0.323
S43. If I can learn real, useful things in the instruction class, this will affect my learning interest.	18.48	19.69	-0.38	0.703
S46. If I feel satisfied with my performance during the instruction process, this will affect my learning interest.	15.38	23.75	-2.84	0.004
Total S	15.83	23.16	-2.06	0.04
A, R, C, S Total	15.79	23.22	-2.07	0.038

Table 2: Post-Intervention GSES Low and High Groups and Their Scores on Each ARCS Motivation Model Component.

($p < 0.05$) were observed in the following three items: R44: "When I had a question, the instructor did not immediately answer it but encouraged me to think or discuss it first. This stimulated my interest in learning." The mean ranks were Group 1 = 19.45, Group 2 = 24.67, Group 3 = 29.25, and Group 4 = 13.43. C45: "The instructor encouraged us to incorporate exercise into our daily lives on our own, which increased my interest in learning." The mean ranks were Group 1 = 19.71, Group 2 = 24.28, Group 3 = 29.00, and Group 4 = 13.43. C48: "When I failed to successfully integrate exercise into my daily life, the instructor asked me to consider whether I had made enough effort, which stimulated my learning interest." The mean ranks were Group 1 = 21.39, Group 2 = 19.56, Group 3 = 31.00, and Group 4 = 13.21. No significant differences were found in the total ARCS motivation model score or in the other individual items among the four groups ($p > 0.05$). These results were presented in table 3.

To further identify specific group differences among the three significant items, a post-hoc multiple comparison was conducted using the Tukey (T) method. For items R44, C45, and C48, significant differences were found between Group 3 and Group 4 ($p < 0.05$). The post-hoc results were presented in table 4.

Free-Text Responses from Participants

Change in GSES: According to Bandura, the maintenance of physiological states—defined as stabilizing both mind and body—is closely associated with GSES. To assess changes in GSES, participants' free-text responses Initial, Midterm, and Final were analyzed for references to maintaining physiological states. These responses were categorized under "psychological health maintenance" and "physical health maintenance," and classified based on evident improvement or decline. The results were shown in tables 5 & 6.

Change in Motivation

To evaluate changes in motivation—particularly in relation to incorporating exercise into daily life—free-text responses from Initial, Midterm, and Final were examined. Content was extracted according to the four components of the ARCS motivation model, and the responses were categorized based on whether a clear improvement or decline was indicated. The results were presented in tables 7 & 8.

Discussion

This study was conducted to examine the effectiveness of an ICT-Based Baduanjin Exercise Support Program, focusing on self-efficacy and motivation. Based on the results obtained, this section discusses the implications for nursing practice, the limitations of the study, and suggestions for future research.

Participant Demographics

A response rate of 100% was achieved, suggesting that a strong interest in health and physical activity was held by the participants. Among them, 75.3% were female and 24.7% were male. According to a report on physical activity published in *The Lancet*, the rate of physical inactivity in China was reported to exceed 16% for men and 12.2% for women. In alignment with these trends, a greater number of women than men expressed a desire to participate in this study.

Effectiveness of the Baduanjin Exercise Support Program Based on GSES and the ARCS Interest Questionnaire

Relationship Between GSES and the Four Factors of the ARCS Motivation Model: As shown in table 2, higher scores on the GSES were associated with higher total scores on the ARCS motivation

Item	Mean Rank				Kruskal-Wallis	
	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	χ^2	p
A2. If the instructor's explanations are vivid, it will affect my interest in learning.	18.89	24.33	21	22.43	1.805	0.614
A4. If the instructor frequently uses visual aids like pictures and slides, it will affect my interest in learning.	20.84	27.17	15.58	18.14	5.105	0.164
A10. If the instructor includes interesting stories related to the content, it will affect my interest in learning.	19.74	24.11	23	18.71	1.648	0.649
A12. If the instructor allows us to explore the secrets of maintaining exercise by ourselves, it will affect my interest in learning.	19.39	22.67	25.75	19.14	2.121	0.548
A15. If I get the chance to speak or demonstrate at a seminar, it will affect my interest in learning.	19.29	24.89	20.75	20.86	1.63	0.653
A21. If the instructor frequently provides interesting information about exercise to stimulate curiosity, it will affect my interest in learning.	20.71	25.5	21.08	15.93	3.281	0.35
A24. If interesting activities such as group competitions or discussions are included, it will affect my interest in learning.	18.82	22.17	29.75	17.93	5.159	0.161
A27. If the instructor often uses vivid examples for teaching, it will affect my interest in learning.	20.32	24.17	23.83	16.36	2.612	0.455
A33. If the instructor's teaching method is clear and focused, this will affect my interest.	17.95	23.83	22.75	24.14	3.004	0.391
A34. If the instructor lets us explain the material and summarize the rules ourselves, this will affect my learning interest.	19.66	24.67	27.5	14.36	6.239	0.101
Total A	18.21	26.78	24.25	18.36	3.963	0.265
R3. If I understand that what I'm learning now is crucial for my future health, it will affect my interest in learning.	21.95	22.67	19.25	17.79	1.27	0.736
R7. If I can stick to exercising well, it will improve my physical fitness and affect my interest in learning.	20.21	22.33	19.58	22.64	0.524	0.914
R11. If the new knowledge connects with what I've already learned, it will affect my interest in learning.	22.63	18.56	24.25	16.93	2.93	0.403
R13. If I can maintain daily exercise to stay healthy, it will affect my interest in learning.	19.58	26	22.75	16.93	3.548	0.315
R16. If the instructor frequently asks me questions or gives me opportunities to express myself, it will affect my interest in learning.	19.53	25.5	24.67	16.07	3.771	0.287
R19. If the instructor is always available to answer questions, it will affect my interest in learning.	19.71	24.22	19.92	21.29	1.18	0.758
R23. If the teaching pace is neither too fast nor too slow, it will affect my interest in learning.	19.03	27.22	21.33	18.07	3.818	0.282
R28. Knowing that daily exercise helps me stay healthy in the community will affect my interest in learning.	21.18	22.94	20.83	18.14	0.815	0.846
R35. If I get to be a Mini instructor, this will affect my learning interest.	18	25.5	27.33	17.93	5.382	0.146
R38. If I can attend exchange meetings and learn with other participants, this will affect my learning interest.	19.82	22.39	25.83	18.29	2.001	0.572
R44. When we have questions, the instructor doesn't rush to answer but lets us think or discuss first, which will affect my learning interest.	19.45	24.67	29.25	13.43	8.905	0.031
R47. If I realize that learning this exercise instruction well is helpful for learning other healthy activities, this will affect my learning interest.	17.76	24.22	25.25	22	3.629	0.304
R49. If I keep regular exercise, I may be awarded the title of "Excellent Exercise Student." This belief will affect my learning interest.	18.89	21.33	29.25	19.21	4.38	0.223
Total R	18.68	26.67	24.58	16.93	4.102	0.251
C1. When I encounter difficulties in maintaining exercise, receiving timely encouragement from the instructor and regaining confidence will affect my interest in learning.	23.26	21.67	16.25	18.07	2.646	0.449
C5. Realizing that success in exercise comes from effort rather than luck will affect my interest in learning.	19.95	26.78	18.33	18.71	3.515	0.319
C8. I believe that if I keep trying, I will succeed, this belief will affect my interest in learning.	19.82	25.89	16.17	22.07	3.47	0.325
C17. If the instructor guides us to apply exercises to real-life situations, it will affect my interest in learning.	19.16	24.17	22	21.07	1.57	0.666
C22. If the instructor asks us to warm up before exercising and confirms relevant issues, it will affect my interest in learning.	20.39	26.33	22.17	14.79	4.513	0.211
C26. If I can maintain good health, it will affect my interest in learning.	19.79	23.17	23.17	19.64	1.036	0.793
C30. When the instructor says, "constant effort brings success," it will affect my interest in learning.	18.24	25.72	18	25	4.193	0.241
C31. When encountering difficulties, if the instructor patiently demonstrates and explains, this will affect my learning interest.	20.11	25.61	21.17	17.36	2.959	0.398
C37. If the instructor guides us to assess our learning in stages to increase self-awareness, this will affect my learning interest.	19.26	24.67	26.5	16.29	4.733	0.192
C39. If I can set learning goals based on my actual situation, and the goals are neither too easy nor too difficult, this will affect my learning interest.	19.03	24.28	26	17.86	3.464	0.325

C41. The instructor says that scoring well in daily exercise doesn't mean we've learned everything and encourages continued effort. This will affect my learning interest.	18.95	21.11	26.67	21.57	2.316	0.51
C42. If the instructor often points out my weaknesses and believes I can improve, this will affect my learning interest.	18.63	24.17	24.17	20.64	2.57	0.463
C45. The instructor requires us to independently complete daily regular exercise, which will affect my learning interest.	19.71	24.28	29	13.43	8.685	0.034
C48. If I fail to maintain daily exercise and the instructor asks me to reflect on whether I'm working hard enough, this will affect my learning interest.	21.39	19.56	31	13.21	8.611	0.035
Total C	19.08	26.17	25.25	15.93	4.221	0.239
S6. If I can learn first and help other participants, it will affect my interest in learning.	21.26	24.72	19	17.21	2.093	0.553
S9. Receiving praise or rewards from the instructor for daily exercise will affect my interest in learning.	19.18	27.83	21.5	16.71	5.054	0.168
S14. When I make mistakes in maintaining exercise, the instructor writes comments like "I believe you can correct this"—this will affect my interest in learning.	21.61	22	22	17.21	1.044	0.791
S18. If the instructor reviews and corrects our exercise performance in a timely manner, helping us understand our mistakes, it will affect my interest in learning.	19.63	26.44	23.33	15.71	4.365	0.225
S20. When the instructor encourages my small improvements, it will affect my interest in learning.	19.84	23.22	22.17	20.29	0.706	0.872
S25. If attending a seminar doesn't make me nervous, it will affect my interest in learning.	17.05	25.33	23.5	24	5.237	0.155
S29. When I open feedback emails from the instructor, seeing "good" evaluations frequently affects my interest in learning.	17.39	24.78	25.25	22.29	4.003	0.261
S32. When learning new knowledge, if the instructor constantly encourages and supports us, this will affect my learning interest.	17.53	27.17	24	19.93	5.616	0.132
S36. If I can learn about every bit of progress from the instructor in a timely manner, this will affect my learning interest.	17.5	27.22	23.33	20.5	5.29	0.152
S40. If my performance in the exercise instruction process is fully recognized by the instructor, this will affect my learning interest.	17.89	24.72	24.5	21.64	3.213	0.36
S43. If I can learn real, useful things in the instruction class, this will affect my learning interest.	20.26	23.72	21.67	18.93	0.96	0.811
S46. If I feel satisfied with my performance during the instruction process, this will affect my learning interest.	19.32	22.39	27	18.64	3.016	0.389
Total S	17.76	27.33	24.5	18.64	4.747	0.191
A, R, C, S Total	18.39	27	24.92	17	4.59	0.204
Group 1<25%						
25%< Group2 <50%						
50%< Group3 <75%						
75%< Group						

Table 3: Differences in ARCS Motivation Model Component and Item Scores Among Four Groups Based on GSES Score Change (Post-Pre) in the Intervention Group.

Item	Four Groups Based on Changes in GSES Scores		p
R44. When I have questions, the instructor does not readily provide answers, encouraging me to think for myself or discuss with others first. This approach generates interest in my learning.	1		0.021
	2		
	3]	
	4		
C45. The instructor asked us to incorporate exercise into our daily lives on our own, which is likely to generate interest in my learning.	1		0.026
	2]	
	3		
C48. If I do not successfully incorporate exercise into my daily life, the instructor asks me to reflect on whether I am putting in enough effort. This generates interest in my learning.	1		0.01
	2		
	3]	
	4		

Table 4: Multiple Comparisons of ARCS Motivation Model Component and Item Scores Across Four Groups Based on GSES Score Change (Post-Intervention) in the ICT Intervention Group.

Perspective	Change	Initial stage	Midterm stage	Final stage
Maintaining Mental Health	Improve	Exercise feels really good afterward	Exercise feels really good afterward	
			Feeling energetic, improved mental state compared to before I feel good.	Helps to calm the mind
			After practice, I can regain peace of mind and reflect on myself. I can also improve concentration.	Exercise feels really good afterward. It feels very pleasant.
	Decline	After the first practice, I didn't feel much	Not much change during this time	
Maintaining Physical Health	Improve	Felt very relaxed	My body felt a bit more comfortable and very relaxed	I can relax
		Felt like I had stretched my body well	Although the movement was very slow, I felt my body stretch and become comfortable. It's good aerobic exercise. I could feel the lower body muscles stretch.	Effective for physical health. Exercise strengthens the body and increases lung capacity.
			I could breathe comfortably	
			As a aerobic exercise, it also felt good for digestion	Digestion in the gastrointestinal tract improved
			Exercise strengthens the body and enhances the immune system	
		Sweating a little	I sweat during exercise	Slight sweating occurred
			My body became warm after exercise	I feel I can achieve weight loss
			Fatigue was reduced, and pain was alleviated	I didn't feel tired from work, and fatigue was improved
		Continued exercise can help improve posture		
		Exercise strengthens the body and kills time		
	Decline	Felt breathless, maybe because it's been a while. Tired.	My arms throbbed, and in the long bow-pulling posture, my thighs hurt. During the fourth movement, the back left neck hurt.	Felt a bit tired and sweated a lot due to the heat
Slight headache		Still breathless and sweaty, felt a bit tired	Felt slight pain in my thighs	

Table 5: Changes in self-efficacy in the Intervention Group Classified from Open-Ended Responses.

Perspective	Change	Initial Stage	Mid Stage	Final stage
Maintaining Mental Health	Improve	I feel very good after exercising.	I feel very good after exercising.	I feel very good after exercising. I feel very comfortable.
		I feel refreshed after exercising.	I feel refreshed and overflowing with energy after exercising.	I feel refreshed and energized after exercising.
			I feel comfortable and happy after exercising.	I feel comfortable and happy after exercising.
	Decline	I didn't feel anything on the first day.	I just started learning today, so the power of exercise is not very clear yet.	After exercising, I feel as calm as water.
Maintaining Physical Health	Improve	My body feels relaxed after exercising.	My body feels relaxed after exercising.	My body feels relaxed after exercising.
		My head feels clear after exercising.		My head becomes clearer after exercising.
		Stretching muscles and ligaments throughout the body.	A strong stretching feeling, stretching the whole body and relaxing the muscles.	I feel my whole body stretching and the muscles relaxing.
			Unblock the flow of energy and blood, promoting blood circulation.	I feel blood flows smoothly after exercising.
			I can breathe comfortably.	
			My appetite increases after exercising.	Exercise before bed increases sleep time and improves sleep quality.
			The quality of my sleep has improved.	Effectively controlling blood pressure. Taking antihypertensives + exercise daily stabilizes blood pressure.
			With daily practice, I don't feel high blood pressure.	
			Practice helps regulate blood sugar and is beneficial for diabetes.	Continuing every day lowers blood sugar levels.
			Practice helps treat many age-related diseases.	Exercising every day can help reduce weight.
		Enhances physical strength and immunity, helping to fight COVID-19.	Can improve physical strength and immunity.	
	Decline	I sweat after exercising.	I sweated after exercising.	I sweated after exercising.
		My physical pain eases.	Corrects physical fatigue and returns to normal state. Eases physical pain.	My physical pain is eased.
Exercise promotes health.		Exercise promotes health.	Suitable for healthy exercise.	
	At first, my whole body ached from overdoing it.			
	I was a little tired.	I get tired.	I still feel a bit tired even after exercising.	

Table 6: Changes in self-efficacy in the Non-Intervention Group Classified from Open-Ended Responses.

ARCS Element	Change	Initial stage	Midterm stage	Final stage
Attention	Improve	Simpler and better than Tai Chi	I saw the message from the instructor and remembered again.	
		Already learned Baduanjin before, so it wasn't hard to start	I can exercise even after meals and without space, which is very convenient. It suits all ages. After exercise, my body feels light and energy flows easily.	
	Declined	Forgot to exercise due to being busy with exams and work. Didn't exercise during breaks		Busy with night shifts and exam prep, felt sleepy
Relevance	Improve		Since exercise has a certain body training effect, it's good to do more of it	I feel unhealthy and physically unwell due to lack of exercise
			Practicing is better than not practicing	
Confidence	Improve		Gradually improving, but still need more practice	I'm better at exercising than before
			Sometimes I exercise	
		Let's continue	Continued practice seems effective for breathing	I can continue, let's keep going
	Decline		Gradually got used to it	Getting used to it
			I really like exercise, so I enjoy practicing.	I love it.
		Can't keep up, poor technique, movements not up to standard	In the first practice, couldn't master the movements. Need more practice. Forgot to breathe during the exercise, couldn't do it well.	
	If I follow my thoughts, I don't want to move	I lack motivation and exercise awareness. I think exercise for health is good, but continuing is hard.	I didn't want to do it, skipped the 5th movement, didn't persist	
Satisfaction	Improve		I make slightly simpler adjustments like walking or bathing before and after Baduanjin. I adjust my exercise plan based on my condition. I feel better and satisfied with the exercise.	I adjust appropriately before and after Baduanjin with walking or bathing. It's slightly simpler than usual and very comfortable. I feel satisfied with the exercise.
			It might be more effective to exercise with others	Let's all try hard
			I look forward to evening exercise time	
		Exercise is very important. I want to exercise when I have time. Planning the next session.	Continuing to exercise is necessary. I plan to go outside and exercise when I have time.	

Table 7: Changes in “Motivation” in the Intervention Group Classified from Free Descriptions.

model. This relationship suggested that motivation levels, as measured by the ARCS model, were influenced by GSES. It has been reported by Suzuki that GSES was beneficial for maintaining and continuing learning or when providing support for such activities, indicating a close connection between GSES and motivation [11]. Moreover, the activity control theory proposed by Kohl (1984) and the concept of GSES were foundational elements of the ARCS model, thereby reinforcing the strong relationship between these two constructs [11]. The increase in GSES suggests that participants are more likely to continue exercising even when faced with difficulties, which is a key element of behavior change in hypertension prevention. Furthermore, maintaining interest and motivation toward exercise supports the sustainability of behavior, so the improvement in motivation through this program is likely to lead to the implementation of hypertension prevention behaviors.

Relationship Between Changes in GSES Scores and the ARCS Motivation Model in the ICT-based intervention group: As indicated in table 3, changes in GSES scores among participants in the ICT-based intervention group were found to be associated with three specific items within the ARCS motivation model (R44, C45, and C48). These changes were shown to influence two ARCS components: Relevance (R) and Confidence (C). Through multiple comparisons, significant differences were observed between Group 3 and Group 4 in terms of GSES score changes, indicating that greater improvements in GSES were accompanied by more favorable outcomes in the Relevance and Confidence domains.

Yang’s findings further supported this result, having demonstrated that the ARCS motivation model—compared to conventional instructional approaches—was associated with enhanced GSES, a greater sense of achievement, increased enjoyment of physical activity, and a more positive attitude toward exercise [12]. In the present study, it was shown that the Baduanjin Exercise Support Program was linked to improvements in GSES and in two components of the ARCS model: Relevance and Confidence. Given that higher GSES was found to promote greater motivation, it was considered essential to implement strategies that enhanced GSES, especially in individuals who initially displayed low exercise motivation for daily life integration. Therefore, it was inferred that this exercise support program had the potential to enhance motivation by improving GSES.

Regarding Free-Text Responses from Participants

Self-efficacy: Maintaining a Healthy Condition: In the ICT-based intervention group, continuous positive feedback and advice were provided by instructors via WeChat. This interaction was considered to have functioned as immediate feedback. As both the ICT and paper-based intervention groups demonstrated more improvements than declines in self-efficacy, it was inferred that the program had a positive effect on enhancing self-efficacy. A high number of comments related to physical health maintenance were observed in both groups, suggesting that the benefits of Baduanjin exercise were recognized. In the ICT-based intervention group, the constant accessibility of video content was believed to have contributed to this outcome. Moreover, participants’ awareness of specific physical changes, such as improvements in blood pressure, was likely influenced by the

ARCS Element	Change	Initial stage	Midterm stage	Final stage
Attention	Improve	The movements are simple and easy to learn	Exercise is good, and I like it It's almost like walking, allowing me to train my body anytime. It's very convenient and manageable, making it a very good form of exercise. It would be helpful to have regular reminders and videos that can be watched directly.	I am very interested in sports. Baduanjin is suitable for small spaces and easy to maintain. It is appropriate for middle-aged and older adults, with gentle movements that can be practiced year-round. It is simple and easy to learn.
	Decline	No time to exercise today	I have specific reasons for not continuing—it's too hot to practice, and I feel sleepy.	On weekdays, commuting and taking care of household chores and children leave me with no time, and it is truly overwhelming.
Relevance	Improve	Great benefit	If I try hard, I should get good results Even though there's no clear improvement, exercising is better than doing nothing	Practicing hard and waiting for results. If I work hard for a few years, there should be benefits.
Confidence	Improve	I'm not good at it, so I need more practice. I feel a bit better than yesterday. The movements are relatively standard.	Gradually getting used to it, but still not fully coordinated. The more I practiced, the more familiar it felt. I felt a bit better and in a better mood than yesterday. "I am grateful for the teacher's guidance and reminders."	The movements are relatively standard. I guarantee to exercise 3–5 times a week I will continue practicing I worked hard this time by following the teacher's guidance.
		Let's continue working hard every day	I want to keep exercising every day	I've formed a habit of exercising once a day
	Decline	Honestly, I'm lazy, so I don't usually exercise much, so it's a bit difficult.	"Exercise is for maintaining health, but..." "The movement and breathing are not in harmony, and diaphragmatic breathing is insufficient. The 5th movement is difficult, and the 2nd movement causes knee pain when squatting."	Endurance is difficult, but there is hope for endurance.
		Unskilled		
Satisfaction	Improve		Life lies in movement. People our age need proper exercise. I adjust the movements, time, and place accordingly, and I truly enjoy the positive changes exercise brings to my body. I make time to practice with my child. We try hard and practice diligently. We must learn from others too.	I adjust the movements, time, and space appropriately according to my physical condition. I really enjoy the changes that exercise brings to the body. Practicing with family gave me strength. I had contact with Qigong Baduanjin before, and I enjoyed this time's exercise. Practicing was fun, and continuing isn't difficult. I feel hopeful from practicing Baduanjin
			It involves cooperating with the research theme, and without this prerequisite, it would be difficult to continue.	This study is very meaningful, and I hope it helps society I started exercising to cooperate with the research, but now I practice once a day voluntarily
		It's okay	"Very good feeling"	feels good. I'm okay today
				With the continued development of science and technology, it has become possible to exercise better and more safely at home, helping maintain health and promoting wider participation in physical activity.

Table 8: Changes in “Motivation” in the paper-based intervention group Classified from Free Descriptions.

individualized daily feedback that was provided by instructors, indicating that personalized guidance affected participants’ awareness of their physical condition.

Motivation to Incorporate Healthy Habits into Daily Life: In Terms of the ARCS Model: Participants’ motivation was examined using the four elements of the ARCS motivation model: Attention (A), Relevance (R), Confidence (C), and Satisfaction (S). Compared to the paper-based intervention group, the ICT-based intervention group demonstrated clearer expressions of motivation across all four factors. Throughout the course of the program—from the beginning to the Midterm and then to Final, an increasing trend in exercise motivation for daily life integration was observed in the ICT-based intervention group, whereas both self-efficacy and motivation declined in the paper-based intervention group. From the Midterm to Final of the intervention, satisfaction was reported to have improved. Reflections conducted at these points were believed to have contributed to this improvement. Additionally, comments expressing a desire to emulate peers suggested the influence of group reflection. As both groups provided more specific free-text responses at the Midterm and Final, it was inferred that feedback during these periods had a positive effect.

Regarding “A: Attention”: Changes in “Attention” were observed over time—from the beginning to the Midterm, and post-intervention. At the beginning, comments such as “I’m not good at it, so I’ll practice more” and “I’ll keep working hard every day” were made by the ICT-based intervention group, suggesting an increase in attention. At

the Midterm, declines in attention were noted in the paper-based intervention group, with statements like “It’s a bit boring, tiring, and not very interesting.” By the Final, this downward trend continued in the paper-based intervention group, whereas the ICT-based intervention group demonstrated improvement. The component of “Attention,” expressed through initial interest or novelty such as “This looks fun” or “I want to try it,” appeared to diminish over time. In the ICT-based intervention group, sustained attention was likely facilitated by the ease of engaging with the video content. Regular reminders were also presumed to have been effective in maintaining engagement. In contrast, the motivation in the paper-based intervention group seemed to rely more on intrinsic interest. Additionally, requests for instructor feedback indicated that ongoing communication with instructors significantly affected motivation.

Regarding “R: Relevance”: In the ICT-based intervention group, motivational changes were evident at the beginning, Midterm, and post-intervention stages, with comments such as “It seems likely to lead to good results” and “It seems worthwhile” indicating increased relevance. In contrast, no comments suggesting improved relevance were found in the paper-based intervention group. “Relevance” referred to the extent to which the activity was perceived as personally meaningful. In the ICT-based intervention group, improvements in relevance were believed to have resulted from ongoing feedback, instructor encouragement, and communication with peers. Although these comments reflected some improvement, the overall low

frequency of relevance-related statements in both groups suggested that the activity might have lacked elements that clearly conveyed personal significance or value.

Regarding “C: Confidence”: In the ICT-based intervention group, a gradual increase in expressions indicating enhanced confidence and satisfaction was observed over time, while expressions of decline decreased. Conversely, in the paper-based intervention group, comments reflecting improved confidence and satisfaction were fewer and declined over time, while negative expressions increased. In the ARCS motivation model, “Confidence” referred to the expected likelihood of success in various activities. Strategies to enhance this expectation and support beliefs such as “I can do it if I try” were considered essential. In the ICT group, confidence appeared to have been influenced by participants perceived progress in learning Baduanjin. Comments such as “I was encouraged by the instructor’s message” suggested that instructor feedback messages delivered daily had a positive impact on participants’ confidence.

Regarding “S: Satisfaction”: In the ICT-based intervention group, an increase in satisfaction was observed from the beginning through to the Final, with a decline in negative expressions over time. In contrast, the paper-based intervention group showed fewer expressions of satisfaction, and the frequency of negative comments increased. “Satisfaction,” which referred to the joy of achieving something challenging and valuable, was considered a crucial factor in sustaining motivation. In the ICT-based intervention group, it was inferred that tailored instructor feedback messages of encouragement and advice, designed to support participants’ sense of accomplishment, had reinforced both confidence and satisfaction. Satisfaction was particularly noted to have improved from the Midterm to the Final, possibly because of structured reflections. Comments indicating that participants learned from peers further underscored the impact of group reflections. In the paper-based intervention group, improvements noted at the Midterm and Final were also attributed to instructor feedback.

Based on the discussion above, participants’ free-text responses suggested that the immediacy of feedback from instructors, recognition from others (instructors and peers), communication among participants, and mid-program reflections in the ICT-based Baduanjin exercise support program had positively influenced and appeared to have enhanced both self-efficacy and motivation.

Limitations and Future Directions of the Study

In this study, a convenience sampling method was employed for participant allocation, which resulted in an imbalance between the ICT-based intervention group and the paper-based intervention group. Consequently, a pre-post comparison design was adopted within each group. Therefore, the validity of participant allocation should be examined in future research through more rigorous sampling strategies.

In addition, the short duration of the study introduced considerable individual differences among participants (e.g., age, occupation, and place of residence), which may have limited the clarity of results when comparing the GSES and the ARCS Motivation Mode. Thus, future studies should consider extending the intervention period and employing strategies to minimize the influence of individual variability.

This study, which implemented an ICT-based Baduanjin exercise support program as a lifestyle intervention, indicated a positive effect on exercise motivation for daily life integration and a tendency

toward increased willingness to engage in physical activity. Based on these findings, it was suggested that ICT-based exercise support programs could be utilized in other contexts to enhance individuals’ self-care ability related to physical activity.

Moreover, in Japan, no prior intervention studies were identified that incorporated Baduanjin into an ICT-based exercise support program. In view of the current results, it was considered necessary to develop a culturally adapted program that could be applied to Japanese society with the aim of improving adults’ self-care abilities related to physical activity.

Due to environmental restrictions caused by the spread of COVID-19, in-person instruction for the initial introduction of the program could not be implemented. Although the non-intervention group had originally been scheduled to receive all instructions face-to-face and conduct the program using printed materials, instructor feedback messages, midterm and final reflections, and surveys were all conducted through synchronous online communication. As a result, the study could not be characterized as a pure comparison between face-to-face instruction and ICT-based instruction. Therefore, it was recommended that future studies clearly define implementation conditions to allow for more accurate and meaningful comparisons.

Baduanjin is a form of health-promoting Qigong exercise rooted in traditional Chinese medicine, with a history spanning several centuries. In recent years, multiple studies have reported its effectiveness in preventing and improving hypertension among adults. However, to achieve the benefits of Baduanjin, it is essential to engage in the practice continuously as part of daily life, rather than through one-time efforts. Sustaining behavioral changes for hypertension prevention requires ongoing motivation and practical support; without this, even effective exercise methods may fail to yield results. In this regard, this program offers regular guidance and encouragement through videos and messages, visualizes progress, promotes interaction with other participants, and incorporates self-monitoring and feedback functions. These features help enhance participants’ sustained motivation and self-efficacy, thereby contributing to the habituation of health-promoting behaviors. Thus, by combining traditional health practices such as Baduanjin with ICT-based support, it becomes possible to implement such practices in a way that fits modern lifestyles, facilitating more effective and sustainable engagement in hypertension prevention behaviors.

Conclusion

This study was conducted to enhance self-care ability through a lifestyle intervention that was implemented using an ICT-based Baduanjin exercise support program. Based on the findings, it was suggested that the ICT-based Baduanjin exercise support program tended to improve self-efficacy and exercise motivation for daily life integration. Furthermore, the results indicated that ICT-based exercise support contributed to improvements in the Relevance (R) and Confidence (C) components of exercise motivation for daily life integration. These outcomes underscored the importance of developing intervention strategies that were aimed at enhancing self-efficacy. In the future, it will be necessary to specifically examine the impact of continued exercise on hypertension prevention and improvements in blood pressure values through long-term follow-up studies. The motivational effects of this program have the potential to promote long-term behavior change and serve as practical support for the prevention of lifestyle-related diseases.

Acknowledgment

Sincere gratitude was extended to all the research participants and their families for the cooperation that was provided during the conduct of this study.

Declaration of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

1. Chinese Hypertension Prevention and Treatment Guidelines Revision Committee (2018) Chinese Hypertension Prevention and Treatment Guidelines, 2018 Revision, Chinese Hypertension Prevention and Treatment Guidelines Revision Committee, China.
2. Healthy China Action (2020) Healthy China Action (2019-2030). Healthy China Action, China.
3. Ye Y, Zhao F, Sun S, Xiong J, Zheng G (2020) The effect of Baduanjin exercise on health-related physical fitness of college students: A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Exercise Science & Fitness* 18: 1-6.
4. Bandura A (1997) Self-efficacy: The exercise of control. WH Freeman, USA.
5. Suzuki K (2005) Instructional design for e-learning practice. *Journal of the Japanese Society for Educational Technology* 29: 197-205.
6. Suzuki K (2018) Trends in instructional design research and its prospects in nursing education. *Juntendo University Journal of Medical and Nursing Research* 8: 21.
7. Ding D (2013) Knowledge innovation service organization in the medical industry based on e-learning. *Technological Entrepreneurship Monthly* 2013.
8. Liu M, Wu X, Tokunaka K, Yamamoto M (2013) Lifestyle intervention to prevent hypertension in Chinese adults — Development of an information and communication technology (ICT)-based exercise support program using Baduanjin. *International Journal of Japanese Nursing Care Practice and Study* 12.
9. Zhang JX, Schwarzer R (1995) Measuring optimistic self-beliefs: A Chinese adaptation of the General Self-efficacy. *Psychologia: An International Journal of Psychology in the Orient* 38: 174-181.
10. Guo D, Ma Q, Zhao F (2000) The development of the ARCS Interest Questionnaire. *Psychological Development and Education* 2000: 34-38.
11. Ichikawa N, Nemoto A (2016) *The Toolbox of Instructional Design* 101. Hokuto Shoin, Kyoto, Japan.
12. Yang M (2011) Motivation and Continuation Strategies of Japanese Language Learners in Taiwan: A Comparison of Japanese Major and Non-major Learners. *Japanese Language Education* 150: 116-130.

- Advances In Industrial Biotechnology | ISSN: 2639-5665
- Advances In Microbiology Research | ISSN: 2689-694X
- Archives Of Surgery And Surgical Education | ISSN: 2689-3126
- Archives Of Urology
- Archives Of Zoological Studies | ISSN: 2640-7779
- Current Trends Medical And Biological Engineering
- International Journal Of Case Reports And Therapeutic Studies | ISSN: 2689-310X
- Journal Of Addiction & Addictive Disorders | ISSN: 2578-7276
- Journal Of Agronomy & Agricultural Science | ISSN: 2689-8292
- Journal Of AIDS Clinical Research & STDs | ISSN: 2572-7370
- Journal Of Alcoholism Drug Abuse & Substance Dependence | ISSN: 2572-9594
- Journal Of Allergy Disorders & Therapy | ISSN: 2470-749X
- Journal Of Alternative Complementary & Integrative Medicine | ISSN: 2470-7562
- Journal Of Alzheimers & Neurodegenerative Diseases | ISSN: 2572-9608
- Journal Of Anesthesia & Clinical Care | ISSN: 2378-8879
- Journal Of Angiology & Vascular Surgery | ISSN: 2572-7397
- Journal Of Animal Research & Veterinary Science | ISSN: 2639-3751
- Journal Of Aquaculture & Fisheries | ISSN: 2576-5523
- Journal Of Atmospheric & Earth Sciences | ISSN: 2689-8780
- Journal Of Biotech Research & Biochemistry
- Journal Of Brain & Neuroscience Research
- Journal Of Cancer Biology & Treatment | ISSN: 2470-7546
- Journal Of Cardiology Study & Research | ISSN: 2640-768X
- Journal Of Cell Biology & Cell Metabolism | ISSN: 2381-1943
- Journal Of Clinical Dermatology & Therapy | ISSN: 2378-8771
- Journal Of Clinical Immunology & Immunotherapy | ISSN: 2378-8844
- Journal Of Clinical Studies & Medical Case Reports | ISSN: 2378-8801
- Journal Of Community Medicine & Public Health Care | ISSN: 2381-1978
- Journal Of Cytology & Tissue Biology | ISSN: 2378-9107
- Journal Of Dairy Research & Technology | ISSN: 2688-9315
- Journal Of Dentistry Oral Health & Cosmesis | ISSN: 2473-6783
- Journal Of Diabetes & Metabolic Disorders | ISSN: 2381-201X
- Journal Of Emergency Medicine Trauma & Surgical Care | ISSN: 2378-8798
- Journal Of Environmental Science Current Research | ISSN: 2643-5020
- Journal Of Food Science & Nutrition | ISSN: 2470-1076
- Journal Of Forensic Legal & Investigative Sciences | ISSN: 2473-733X
- Journal Of Gastroenterology & Hepatology Research | ISSN: 2574-2566
- Journal Of Genetics & Genomic Sciences | ISSN: 2574-2485
- Journal Of Gerontology & Geriatric Medicine | ISSN: 2381-8662
- Journal Of Hematology Blood Transfusion & Disorders | ISSN: 2572-2999
- Journal Of Hospice & Palliative Medical Care
- Journal Of Human Endocrinology | ISSN: 2572-9640
- Journal Of Infectious & Non Infectious Diseases | ISSN: 2381-8654
- Journal Of Internal Medicine & Primary Healthcare | ISSN: 2574-2493
- Journal Of Light & Laser Current Trends
- Journal Of Medicine Study & Research | ISSN: 2639-5657
- Journal Of Modern Chemical Sciences
- Journal Of Nanotechnology Nanomedicine & Nanobiotechnology | ISSN: 2381-2044
- Journal Of Neonatology & Clinical Pediatrics | ISSN: 2378-878X
- Journal Of Nephrology & Renal Therapy | ISSN: 2473-7313
- Journal Of Non Invasive Vascular Investigation | ISSN: 2572-7400
- Journal Of Nuclear Medicine Radiology & Radiation Therapy | ISSN: 2572-7419
- Journal Of Obesity & Weight Loss | ISSN: 2473-7372
- Journal Of Ophthalmology & Clinical Research | ISSN: 2378-8887
- Journal Of Orthopedic Research & Physiotherapy | ISSN: 2381-2052
- Journal Of Otolaryngology Head & Neck Surgery | ISSN: 2573-010X
- Journal Of Pathology Clinical & Medical Research
- Journal Of Pharmacology Pharmaceutics & Pharmacovigilance | ISSN: 2639-5649
- Journal Of Physical Medicine Rehabilitation & Disabilities | ISSN: 2381-8670
- Journal Of Plant Science Current Research | ISSN: 2639-3743
- Journal Of Practical & Professional Nursing | ISSN: 2639-5681
- Journal Of Protein Research & Bioinformatics
- Journal Of Psychiatry Depression & Anxiety | ISSN: 2573-0150
- Journal Of Pulmonary Medicine & Respiratory Research | ISSN: 2573-0177
- Journal Of Reproductive Medicine Gynaecology & Obstetrics | ISSN: 2574-2574
- Journal Of Stem Cells Research Development & Therapy | ISSN: 2381-2060
- Journal Of Surgery Current Trends & Innovations | ISSN: 2578-7284
- Journal Of Toxicology Current Research | ISSN: 2639-3735
- Journal Of Translational Science And Research
- Journal Of Vaccines Research & Vaccination | ISSN: 2573-0193
- Journal Of Virology & Antivirals
- Sports Medicine And Injury Care Journal | ISSN: 2689-8829
- Trends In Anatomy & Physiology | ISSN: 2640-7752

Submit Your Manuscript: <https://www.heraldopenaccess.us/submit-manuscript>